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From Design to Experimentation in Molecular Communications: Discussion through a Case Study

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Abstract—Molecular communications is an active research area developed in the last quarter of century, trying to combine communications theory results with biological and unconventional environments. The main characteristic of molecular communications is the use of molecules as information carriers instead of electromagnetic signals to implement communications between nanomachines, natural cells, or synthetic ones, able to transmit and receive these signals, which may be useful when electromagnetic communications are not possible or undesirable. However, this new application domain comes with significant issues when it is necessary to switch from design and/or simulation to practical experimentation. In this letter, we critically discuss the transition from design to testbed experimentation, using a practical case study as driving example. The case study is relevant to the application of molecular communications for building a monitoring device, able to detect with local and minimally invasive technology the condition of blood hyperviscosity for continuous patient monitoring. We present the issues arose during the experimentation that have an impact on testbed design, and identify potential, practical solutions to address them, thus providing contributions in the area of testbed and platform design. These methodologies have a general applicability beyond the scope of this specific application, thus offering insights for broader molecular communication applications.

Index Terms—Molecular communications theory, testbed experimentation, experimental data acquisition, implementation issues, bloodstream environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

MOLECULAR communications (MolCom) are a recent research area aiming at porting established research outcomes from telecommunications into new application domains, like medicine and botanic [1]. The main novelty of MolCom is using molecules as information carrier between nanomachines, natural cells, or synthetic/engineered ones. This means that classic electromagnetic (EM) signals are substituted with bursts of molecules with specific properties, and information is encoded in their concentration, their type, their release time, or into a combination of these techniques. When EM communications are impossible, difficult, or undesirable for safety or compatibility issues, as in intra-body scenarios, MolCom can open completely new application domains.

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This opportunity has pushed an intense research activity focused not only on mapping already established research results into these new application domains [2], but also to exploit their unique features. After an initial focus on theoretical aspects [3] and simulation platforms [4], as research results has become mature, we witnessed a concrete effort towards implementation of research results in real testbed [5]–[7]. This is a needed step if the final goal is the realization of a physical device, for instance for monitoring patient health conditions with minimally invasive technology leveraging MolCom [8].

The transition from design to real testbeds may be critical, as the design process as well as simulation approaches often neglect some phenomena that have to be considered during experimentation. The main contribution of this paper is a critical discussion of these issues, identifying also possible and concrete solutions, by referring to a specific and concrete use case of MolCom application. The base for the discussion is a previous work of ours, dealing with the design of a monitoring device for hyperviscosity detection [9]. The hyperviscosity syndrome is an altered blood condition that prevents it from freely flowing in vessels and results in an excessive viscosity of blood, which has to be timely detected, since it significantly increases the risk of many cardiovascular diseases. We carry out the discussion by commenting recent experimental activity on microfluidic communications [10], used to mimic the bloodstream as first step towards complete *in-vivo* testing. This discussion could guide the setup of wet lab testbeds for carrying out MolCom experimental activity, contributing to making this transition as smooth as possible, and preparing researchers to face unforeseen issues. In fact, the identified solutions provide contributions in the area of testbed and platform design, with a general applicability beyond the scope of our specific application.

The paper is organized as follows. In section II, we recall the basic concepts of the design of a monitoring device for hyperviscosity detection. In section III, we discuss an experimental platform that can be used for testing basic phenomena occurring inside blood vessels, highlighting issues arising when theoretical design has to be put into practice. In section IV, we critically discuss our previous findings, offering possible solutions for long term testing activity, enlarging our viewpoint. Finally, section V reports our concluding remarks.

II. ARCHITECTURE OF THE MONITORING DEVICE

The system presented in [9] is aimed at detecting the condition of hyperviscosity without a repeated blood samples analysis. The system leverages the characteristics of physical propagation of nanoparticles in fluids with different viscosity.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of prototypal testbed platform including a detailed drawing of the six-way valve and the switch between the two working positions, loading and inject, respectively. Images showcase the three primary elements of the experimental setup: the pump syringe, the valve system comprising the selection valve (upper) and the injection valve (lower), and the fluorescence detector.

to the concentration $C(t)$ of fluorescent particles at the detection point, according to the relation $\Delta I(t) = k \cdot C(t)$, where k is an instrument- and fluorophore-specific calibration constant. This procedure enables quantitative reconstruction of the concentration profile of the molecular messengers as they travel through the transport channel. The detector's spectral selectivity and integration with a flow cell allow for precise tracking of the temporal dispersion dynamics.

We used carbon dots (CDs) as fluorescent particles. They can be easily synthesized via thermal degradation of organic precursors, such as citric acid, through pyrolysis [10]. The resulting nanoparticles exhibit diameters in the range of 5–20 nm. Their selection was motivated by their high quantum yield, excitation/emission tunability, good aqueous dispersibility, and low cytotoxicity, making them well-suited for applications in MolCom testbeds. In our experiments, the CDs were dispersed in a water–glycerol mixture adjusted to achieve a dynamic viscosity of approximately 3.5 mPa·s, matching that of blood plasma. This choice allows simulating physiologically relevant flow conditions in a controlled environment. The fluorescence detector captures the light emitted by the CDs as they traverse the sensing region, with the measured intensity being directly proportional to the local concentration of particles. Based on the Stokes–Einstein relation and assuming a hydrodynamic diameter of 10 nm, the diffusion coefficient in this medium is estimated to be $D \approx 1.0 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, accounting for the higher viscosity relative to pure water. This value is essential for characterizing the dispersion and arrival time of the molecular messengers at the detection point.

The choice of CDs with respect to other fluorescent technologies, such as FRET-based nanocommunications [13], which use a different physical principle to convey information (Förster Resonance Energy Transfer), is motivated by FRET range. It is really short, in the order of hundreds of nm with multi-step communications, and less than 10 nm for single interaction [14], thus limiting significantly the intensity of signal when nanoparticles get dispersed in the fluid.

The resulting data provide a quantitative measure of the received molecular signals, thus fluorescence detector emulates the one realized by the activated endothelium in Fig. 1, and it is indicated by ③. The integration of these components results in

TABLE I
TESTBED PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Tube diameter ($2R$)	75 μm
Tube length L_C	0.2 m
Fluid flow rate Q	0.5 - 2.58 $\mu\text{L/s}$
Fluid density	1.08 Kg/L
Fluid viscosity	3.5 mPas
Plug viscosity	1, 2.5, 3.5, 5, 7.5 mPas
Nanoparticle diameter	5-20 nm
Nanoparticles diffusion coefficient	$1.0 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$
Peclet number (Pe)	$\approx 4500 \ll \frac{4L_C}{R}$, see [8]
Detector excitation wavelength	365 nm
Detector emission wavelength	450 nm

a cohesive system that has been designed to emulate MolCom in a controlled environment. As the particles travel through the tube, their concentration and time distribution are influenced by diffusion and advection. Upon reaching the sensing point, the fluorescence detector records the fluorescence intensity, thereby providing the experimental data necessary for the analysis of the communication process.

B. Experimental results and challenges

A critical issue encountered during our experimentation pertained to the release of information particles into the communication channel. At design level, it is often assumed that information particles are released in isolation, without any surrounding medium or solvent, as depicted in Fig. 1, where it is assumed particles are released by microneedles ①. This idealized approach simplifies mathematical models but is not easily feasible in practice. In actual testbed scenarios, the information particles must be dissolved in a solvent, typically water or another fluid, to facilitate their injection into the channel. The solvent functions as a carrier, thereby enabling the controlled release and transport of nanoparticles or molecular messengers. However, the introduction of a solvent brings with it a number of significant challenges that fundamentally alter the behaviour of the system. When the plug of information particles, dissolved in a solvent such as water and released by the 6-way valve, reaches the communication channel, it encounters the fluid already in the channel. In the event of a significant disparity in the viscosity of the two fluids, a hydrodynamic instability known as viscous fingering may occur. Within the design framework, a primary objective was to estimate the viscosity of the communication channel by means of analysing the molecular signal received downstream. This approach was predicated on the assumption that the plug of information particles would travel through the channel in a predictable manner, thus preserving its shape and concentration profile. This would, in turn, allow precise correlations to be made between signal dynamics and channel viscosity. However, the emergence of viscous fingering during experimentation introduced a significant complication to this process. While a detailed quantitative analysis of viscous fingering, including dispersion coefficients and signal-to-noise ratio, is outside the scope of this paper, readers are referred to the works in [7] and [10] for a comprehensive discussion on the modeling and experimental validation of these phenomena. The fluorescence

Fig. 3. Experimental fluorescence intensity detected by the receiver placed at a distance of 200 mm from the transmitter (a), and accumulated intensity at the detector (b). The different colors correspond to varying viscosities of the nanoparticle-containing injected plugs and flow rates Q . The transporting flow has a viscosity of 3.5 mPas, which is within the range of physiological plasma viscosity and approximates the overall viscosity of blood under certain conditions.

signal of the cap at the receiver provided clear evidence of these challenges through our testbed experimentation, as shown in Fig. 3.a, showing the signal intensity provided by the fluorescent detector as a function of time, for different values of the plug viscosity. Instead of observing a single, concentrated peak corresponding to the arrival of the molecular signal, a bumpy, multi-peaked profile was detected. This is indicative of signal fragmentation and irregular scattering caused by viscous fingering. The black curve, corresponding to a plug with the same viscosity of the carrier, exhibits a earlier rise time. This is due to different diffusion phenomena, because the concentration gradient is only due to the presence of the nanoparticles dissolved in the plug. Instead, when two components mix, their create interfacial instability, thus implying additional delay and fingering phenomena. When observing accumulated fluorescence intensity in Fig. 3.b, which models even better the signal provided by the detector **3** in Fig. 1, we can appreciate the different outputs due to differences in viscosity more clearly. Higher values of the plug viscosity corresponds to higher total signal, able to alter the final readout. Fig. 4 offers a clear visualization of the fingering phenomenon. It is a false color image showing a snapshot of the concentration of injected nanoparticles dispersed in the flow emulating the blood, when the viscosity of the injected plug is lower than that of the transporting flow.

Finally, according to the results obtained in [9], we expect that when the fluid flow rate is higher, we should obtain an earlier and weaker signal, as nanoparticles do not have the same chances to migrate towards the vessel walls and adhere to the activated endothelium. Black curve (dash-dot) in Fig. 3 provides a clear evidence of this phenomenon when compared with the one (black solid) corresponding to the same viscosity but lower flow rate, thus confirming theory and simulations.

IV. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

Testing MolCom with an experimental setup is challenging, as a broad range of transport media, technologies, and temporal scales have to be considered. If we limit our scope to the experimentation emulating blood vessels, we can still address an ample range of potential health-related applications. First, we address issues related to the application of microfluidic

Fig. 4. Color map obtained by simulation showing the concentration of nanoparticles dispersed in a flow. The injected plug has a lower viscosity than the surrounding fluid ($\eta = 2.5$ mPa-s), generating a well-defined fingering pattern due to the interfacial instability. The simulation was carried out assuming a cylindrical channel of radius $R = 0.1$ mm and length $L = 60$ mm, with fully reflective boundaries. The viscosity of the carrier was set to $\eta = 3.5$ mPa-s, mimicking blood viscosity, and the initial concentration of nanoparticles was $C_0 = 1$ a.u. Diffusion was modeled with a spatially dependent coefficient $D = 1.0 \times 10^{-11}$ m²/s. The instability parameter $\alpha = 0.2$ modulates the anisotropy of the velocity field at the fluid-fluid interface, introducing small perturbations that mimic realistic fluctuations in interfacial tension or local concentration gradients. This allows the simulation to reproduce the emergence of fingering structures during plug dispersion in a more physically representative manner.

testbeds for viscosity estimation, then generalizing to the broader field of applications targeting the bloodstream.

A. Discussion related to hyperviscosity estimation use case

To address the challenges identified in Section III, and converge towards a reliable viscosity estimation, several strategies can be adopted. By selecting a solvent for the plug that matches the viscosity of the channel fluid, the risk of viscous fingering can be minimized. This reduces instability at the interface, allowing the plug to propagate more evenly. This requires a modification of the testbed if the fluid viscosity is unknown. Several plugs with different viscosity should be released in sequence, using a multiple reservoir system and a multi-view selector valve [10]. The one with similar viscosity to the channel fluid will not show fingering and can therefore be used for calculation. Thus, the receiver should

be able to analyze the signal shape to recognize the most suitable one, also adopting machine learning (ML) algorithms. Alternatively, ML could be used to decode distorted signals at the receiver. By training the models on experimental data, channel viscosity can be deduced even in the presence of irregular signal profiles.

In our experimental testbed, RBCs are absent, introducing a significant difference from the in-vivo scenario. In fact, RBCs creates a ‘cell-free layer’ near the vessel walls [8], causing the migration of nanoparticles towards the periphery of the blood stream. Thus, in the test bench, there is a more uniform distribution of particles across the entire cross-section of the channel. To apply experimental results to biological systems involving bloodstream, it is necessary to selectively sample information particles located near the channel boundaries. Techniques such as surface plasmon resonance (SPR) have proven effective in isolating the signal generated by particles near the walls of the testbed, effectively mimicking the behavior of the system that should be observed in-vivo. Consequently, the lack of RBCs in the experimental setup can be compensated for by appropriately scaling the concentration of sampled particles near the edges of the channel, which results inferior to that expected in an in-vivo setup.

B. Discussion about applications involving blood vessels

Blood can be directly used in microfluidic testbeds instead of aqueous solutions, although its usage in experimentation may raise important ethical and practical issues. Use of human blood would require prior approval by an institutional ethics committee and the informed consent of donors. A better alternative is animal blood, particularly bovine blood, which presents fewer ethical and regulatory complexities. We adopt the ‘3Rs’ approach (*replacement, reduction, and refinement*), widely recognized as good practice in biomedical research by using bovine blood obtained from sources where its collection serves purposes unrelated to our experiments and where the material would otherwise be discarded.

Another promising avenue is the development of ‘hybrid’ test benches, i.e. incorporating in-vivo models while interfacing with in-vitro bench instrumentation. One such approach involves the exploitation of extracorporeal circulation protocols, as exemplified by Zucal et al. [15]. It provides a functional circulatory system by connecting an extracorporeal perfusion device to animal cadavers, offering a middle way between traditional in-vitro testbeds and fully in-vivo experiments. By introducing nanoparticles into the perfusion fluid, realistic vascular environments could be simulated, including the interaction between molecules and vessel walls or endothelium. The intact circulatory structure would allow a more accurate representation of blood flow dynamics, including factors such as fluid flow rate, pressure gradients, and wall shear stress. Ethically, the use of animal cadavers eliminates the need for testing on live animals. Furthermore, the reusability of the cadaveric model for multiple experiments reduces the number of animals required (reduction principle). However, since this type of experimental activity may require very specialized expertise, a preliminary setup with microfluidic testbeds is always recommended to avoid wasting precious resources.

V. CONCLUSION

In this letter, we have explored the challenges that can arise when theoretical models of molecular communications are implemented in practical testbeds. In fact, the design process necessarily abstracts the real-world environment, often simplifying or neglecting phenomena apparently non significant for the functioning of the real system, but that, in operational conditions, may represent significant issues to face during experimentation. We addressed a case study dealing with monitoring of blood vessels leveraging MolCom capabilities, discussing the issue of viscous fingering occurring during the release of information particles into the communication channel. As it is necessary to dissolve them in a solvent to facilitate their injection into the channel (an aspect typically neglected at the design level), the viscosity of the solvent may cause this phenomenon. To mitigate this issue, we have explored a number of potential solutions which have an ample scope, well beyond the case study considered in this letter, to be tested in future experiments.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Suda and T. Nakano, “Molecular communication: A personal perspective,” *IEEE Transactions on NanoBioscience*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 424–432, 2018.
- [2] D. Kilinc and O. Akan, “Receiver design for molecular communication,” *Selected Areas in Communications, IEEE Journal on*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 705–714, December 2013.
- [3] M. Pierobon and I. F. Akyildiz, “A physical end-to-end model for molecular communication in nanonetworks,” *IEEE J.Sel. A. Commun.*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 602–611, May 2010.
- [4] V. Jamali et al., “Channel modeling for diffusive molecular communication—a tutorial review,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 107, no. 7, pp. 1256–1301, 2019.
- [5] S. Lotter et al., “Experimental research in synthetic molecular communications – part i,” *IEEE Nanotechnology Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 42–53, 2023.
- [6] —, “Experimental research in synthetic molecular communications – part ii,” *IEEE Nanotechnology Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 54–65, 2023.
- [7] F. Cali, L. Fichera, and N. Tuccitto, “Comprehensive step-by-step procedure to setup a molecular communication through liquid experiment,” *MethodsX*, vol. 9, p. 101736, 2022.
- [8] L. Felicetti, M. Femminella, and G. Reali, “Molecular communications in blood vessels: Models, analysis, and enabling technologies,” *Communications of the ACM*, no. 3, 2025.
- [9] L. Felicetti, M. Femminella, and G. Reali, “A molecular communications system for live detection of hyperviscosity syndrome,” *IEEE Transactions on NanoBioscience*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 410–421, 2020.
- [10] F. Cali, G. Li-Destri, and N. Tuccitto, “Interfacial shift keying allows a high information rate in molecular communication: Methods and data,” *IEEE Transactions on Molecular, Biological, and Multi-Scale Communications*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 300–307, 2023.
- [11] A. S. AL-Japairai et al., “Current trends in polymer microneedle for transdermal drug delivery,” *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, vol. 587, p. 119673, Sep. 2020.
- [12] K. M. Graczyk, D. Strzelczyk, and M. Matyka, “Deep learning for diffusion in porous media,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 13, no. 1, Jun. 2023.
- [13] M. Kusecu, A. Kiraz, and O. B. Akan, “Fluorescent molecules as transceiver nanoantennas: The first practical and high-rate information transfer over a nanoscale communication channel based on fret,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 5, no. 1, Jan. 2015.
- [14] M. Kusecu and O. B. Akan, “Multi-step fret-based long-range nanoscale communication channel,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 31, no. 12, p. 715–725, Dec. 2013.
- [15] I. Zucal, A.-L. Feder, T. Kyaw, S. Khin, P. I. Heidekrueger, L. Prantl, S. Haerteis, and T. Aung, “An innovative simulation model for microvascular training,” *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, vol. 150, no. 1, pp. 189e–193e, 2022.